

REPORT:

A2.2.2: Development of test protocols for microfluidic devices

Work package 2

<https://mfmet.eu>

This report was written as part of activity 2.2.2 from the EMPIR Establishing Metrology Standards in Microfluidic Devices (MFMET) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1st June 2021 and focused on providing a generic methodology of accurate measurement of a particular quantity in a microfluidic device by utilising standardised methods and reference documents, e.g. VIM & GUM. For more details about this project, please visit www.mfmet.eu

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The EMPIR initiative is co-funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the EMPIR Participating States

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1. Scope

This document provides test protocols for specific microfluidic measurements of the quantities:

- flow resistivity
- flow
- volume
- volume of droplets

Activity number	Activity description	Partners (Lead in bold)
A2.2.2 M14	Using input from A2.2.1 and the generic methodology defined in A2.1.1, NEL, INESC MN, CETIAT, IPQ, CMI, TUBITAK and BHT will develop test protocols for at least 3 flow quantities (such as flow rate, flow speed, and liquid volume) related to microfluidic devices, and ensuring traceability to national standard and conformity to existing normative standards.	DTI , CETIAT, IPQ, CMI, TUBITAK, BHT, INESC MN

Flow rate ranges and calibration methods available at National Metrology Institutes are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1 – Summary of established methods to calibrate flow rates and associated ranges of uncertainty and accuracy.

Flow rate	Calibration Method	Uncertainty ^a	Accuracy ^b	Accuracy ^c
Low flow rate 1 nl/min to 1 µl/min	Optical (preferably); Low-flow displacement	~ 1%	10 % 0.2 - 1.5 µl/min	2 % FS ^b 0.083 - 33 µl/min
Middle flow rate 1 µl/min to 100 µl/min (hot spot)	Gravimetry; Displacement	~ 0.5%	5 % 6 - 110 µl/min	0.2 % Rd ^c 0.83 - 3300 µl/min
High flow rate 100 µl/min to 10 ml/min	Gravimetry	~ 0.1%	5 % 1.2 - 8 ml/min	0.2 % Rd ^c 16.7 - 33300 µl/min

^a National Metrology Standards; ^b Sensirion sensor; ^c Bronkhorst sensor; ^dFS – full scale ^e Rd - reading

2. Flow Resistivity

2.1. Flow rate vs. pressure difference

2.1.1. Description of the test

The measurement of flow resistivity is used to determine the necessary pressure to achieve the desired flow through a microfluidic circuit, or conversely, to determine the flow rate corresponding to a given inlet pressure. Flow resistivity measurement consists of measuring the differential pressure (or solely the inlet pressure if the outlet is at atmospheric pressure) of a given microfluidic circuit and measuring the flow passing through the same microfluidic circuit, either simultaneously or sequentially, for at least one (preferably several) couple flow rate/pressure. The output of this test can be a table of results and/or a graphical representation of Flow vs. Pressure. The flow resistivity is given in Pa.s/m³.

2.1.2. Measurand

Flow resistance, also called hydrodynamic resistance or just microfluidic resistance, corresponds to the opposition that a fluidic element, like a pipe, offers to a flow through itself. Each element of a microfluidic circuit offers some resistance to the flow which is translated into a drop of pressure. As example, considering a straight channel with no contractions, expansions, bends, elbows, etc., small Reynolds numbers of around 1, incompressible fluid, unidirectional and steady flow and small fluid mass per distance unit, so gravity is negligible, the pressure drop in the flow system can be calculated by using the Hagen-Poiseuille relation:

$$\Delta P = QR_H \quad (2.1)$$

where ΔP is the pressure difference, or drop, between two points along the system, Q is the flow rate and R_H is the hydraulic resistance.

Considering that the pressure drop associated with any section of microchannel depends on the flow rate, the dimensions and shape of the channel and the dynamic viscosity of the fluid, the hydraulic resistance for the most typical channel cross sections, i.e. circle, rectangle and square, are respectively:

$$R_{Hc} = \frac{8\mu L}{\pi r^4} \quad R_{H,rec} = \frac{12\mu L}{1-0,63\left(\frac{h}{w}\right)} \left(\frac{1}{h^3 w}\right) \quad R_{H,sq} = \frac{12\mu L}{1-0,917 \times 0,63} \left(\frac{1}{h^4}\right) \quad (2.2)$$

where r is the radius of the circle, μ is the dynamic viscosity, L is the length of the channel, h is the height of the channel and w is the width of the channel.

2.1.3. Test method

Measuring flow resistivity across a microfluidic device is performed using at least a pressure pressure controller (Figures 1-3), which includes one pressure source and element(s) to stabilize and control the pressure such as a control valve, one flow sensor (F), and either:

- a. one pressure sensor (P) at the device's inlet. The device outlet left at atmospheric pressure.

Figure 1: One pressure sensor. F represents the flow sensor, P represents the pressure sensor.

- b. one differential pressure sensor in parallel with the microfluidic device.

Figure 2: One differential pressure sensor. F represents the flow sensor, P represents the pressure sensor.

- c. two pressure sensors, one connected at the microfluidic device inlet and another at the outlet.

Figure 3: Two pressure sensors. F represents the flow sensor, P represents the pressure sensor.

2.1.4. Set up and test equipment

To mount and use the schematics above, it is necessary to meet the following specifications:

Pressure controller:

- The pressure controller must be chosen according to the admissible pressure range in the microfluidic device. Generally, a pressure controller should be used in 10 - 90 % of its pressure range capability.
- The stability of the pressure controller must be in accordance with the accuracy required for the pressure drop/flow resistivity measurement. This information can be found in the datasheet of the pressure controller. Note that the stability can be degraded due to the compliance (elasticity) of the entire setup and dead volumes which can entrap air (in case of a liquid as the test media).
- A sufficient pressure level at the pressure source (inlet) of the pressure controller should be provided prior to measurement. The minimum and maximum pressure level can be found in the datasheet of the pressure controller. The same apply for the required electrical power supply.
- The pressure controller should be at the same altitude as the microfluidic device.
- Minimum pressure at the outlet of the pressure controller is generally ~ 100 mbar to ensure good pressure control and stability.

Pressure sensor(s), differential pressure sensor:

- It must be chosen according to the pressure range (or pressure drop range in case of a differential pressure sensor) to be measured in the microfluidic device. Generally, a pressure sensor should be used between 10% and 100% of its pressure range capability.
- The accuracy of the pressure sensor must be in accordance with the accuracy required for the pressure drop / flow resistivity measurement. This information can be found in the datasheet of the pressure sensor. Note that this accuracy can be degraded due to the compliance (elasticity) of the entire setup and dead volumes which can entrap air (in case of a liquid as the test media).
- The pressure sensor(s) should be at the same altitude as the microfluidic device.

- All pressure sensors should be calibrated before any pressure measurements. The calibration should be performed by a ISO17025:2017 accredited laboratory.
- In case of a liquid as the test media, the tubing connecting the pressure sensor(s) to the pressure controller and microfluidic device should be set downward so that air bubbles are expelled (purged) downstream of the setup.
- In case of a gas as the test media, the tubing connecting the pressure sensor(s) to the pressure controller and microfluidic device should be set upward so that liquid droplets (due for example to condensation of humidity) are expelled (purged) downstream of the setup.

Flow sensor:

- It must be chosen according to the flow range to be measured in the microfluidic device. Generally, a flow sensor should be used between 10% and 100% of its pressure range capability.
- The accuracy of the flow sensor must be in accordance with the accuracy required for the pressure drop / flow resistivity measurement. This information can be found in the datasheet of the flow sensor. Note that this accuracy can be degraded due to the compliance (elasticity) of the entire setup and dead volumes which can entrap air (in case of a liquid as the test media).
- All flow sensors should be calibrated before any pressure measurements. The calibration should be performed by a ISO17025:2017 accredited laboratory.
- In case of a liquid as the test media, the tubing connecting the flow sensor(s) to the pressure controller and microfluidic device should be set downward so that air bubbles are expelled (purged) downstream of the setup.
- In case of a gas as the test media, the tubing connecting the flow sensor(s) to the pressure controller and microfluidic device should be set upward so that liquid droplets (due for example to condensation of humidity) are expelled (purged) downstream of the setup.

Fittings/connectors:

- All fittings and connectors should be chosen and set keeping in mind that any leakage will cause measurement error and will degrade the flow resistivity accuracy.
- All fittings and connectors should be chosen as to minimize their dead volume.

2.1.5. Test conditions

Measurements should be performed in a temperature and humidity-controlled room. Temperature, ambient pressure, and humidity fluctuations range should be known, either by measurement (using calibrated sensors) or by knowledge of the control ranges, ensuring that the climate-control system (air-conditioning for example) is performing normally. Ideal conditions are 23 ± 2 °C and 55 ± 5 % HR.

2.1.6. Preparation

All elements of the setup (pressure controller, measurements sensors, test media, and microfluidic devices) should be left in the room where the tests are to be performed at least 24 hours before the test, to ensure thermal equilibrium. Electrically powered elements such as the pressure controller and the pressure sensor(s) should be powered on at least 30 minutes before beginning any measurement. For pressure controllers requiring the filling of a reservoir, the latter should be filled beforehand, at least 30 minutes before beginning any measurement. The entire system, including pressure taps in case of differential pressure sensor, should be purged before beginning any measurement. Purge can

be performed using the test media at the maximum admissible pressure of the pressure controller/pressure sensor(s)/microfluidic device (whichever has the lesser maximum admissible pressure).

2.1.7. Test procedure

Keeping in mind the requirements stated in paragraphs 2.1.3 to 2.1.6:

1. Dispose of all setup elements in the room where the test are to be performed, for at least 24 hours before beginning any measurement
2. Connect all elements together to mount the setup, making sure that all fittings are tightly connected.
3. If necessary, fill the pressure controller reservoir at least 30 minutes before beginning any measurement.
4. Connect all required electrical power supplies to the pressure controller and pressure sensor(s), and power on at least 30 minutes before beginning any measurement.
5. Purge the setup using the test media at the maximum admissible pressure of the pressure controller/pressure sensor(s)/microfluidic device (whichever has the lesser maximum admissible pressure)
6. Zero the pressure and flow sensors to minimize any measurement offset
7. Set a target pressure to the pressure controller and monitor the evolution of the pressure using the pressure sensor(s).
8. After reaching a stable pressure (not drifting upwards or downwards), record the measurement.
9. Repeat step 7 and 8 for all required target pressure.
10. In case of a differential pressure sensor or two pressure sensors, remove the microfluidic device and connect directly both pressure taps in order to measure the pressure taps pressure drops. Repeat step Repeat step 7 and 8 for all measured flows in the previous steps.
11. Calculate each flow resistivity according to equation (1) of paragraph 2.1.2. In case of a differential pressure sensor or two pressure sensors, subtract the pressure taps pressure drops to the calculated device's pressure drop.
12. An example of flow and pressure drop measurement is shown in the figure below, for 4 different flow and pressure measurements steps.

Figure 4: pressure drop and flow rate measurements [1]

2.2. Dry evaluation of flow resistivity

Dry calibration consists in using the dimensional measurement of the microfluidic device to calculate its flow resistivity. If possible, all needed dimensions should be measured using a ISO17025:2017 calibrated instruments with a measurement resolution and accuracy in agreement with the target measurement uncertainty.

Examples of dry evaluation of flow resistivity are given at:

<https://www.elveflow.com/microfluidic-reviews/general-microfluidics/flow-resistance/>

https://en.wikibooks.org/wiki/Microfluidics/Hydraulic_resistance_and_capacity

3. Flow

3.1. Gravimetric method

3.1.1. Description of the test

The gravimetric method is used to determine a delivered mass of a liquid over a time interval. The method can be used on measurements for both inline flow sensors and flow generators. To achieve the measurements a weighing vessel, placed on a balance, collects the liquid to determine the mass delivered. While the delivery time interval for the collection of the mass is determined as well.

3.1.2. Measurand

Flow describes the unit quantity delivered over a unit time. Fluid flow related to the gravimetric method consists of mass flow rate $\left[\frac{kg}{s}\right]$ and volume flow rate $\left[\frac{m^3}{s}\right]$. The mass flow rate relates the delivered mass to the delivery time and the volume flow rate relates the delivered mass in the mass flow rate to the delivered volume presented in eq. 3.1 and 3.2 respectively:

$$q_m = \frac{m}{t} = \frac{m_1 - m_0}{t} \left(\frac{1 - \frac{\rho_a}{\rho_p}}{1 - \frac{\rho_a}{\rho_w}} \right) \quad (3.1)$$

and

$$q_V = \frac{q_m}{\rho_w t} = \frac{m_1 - m_0}{\rho_w t} \left(\frac{1 - \frac{\rho_a}{\rho_p}}{1 - \frac{\rho_a}{\rho_w}} \right) \quad (3.2)$$

According to IEC60601-2-24 [2] and TIR 101 [3] and Bissig and al [4] corrections for needle buoyancy, evaporation, and surface tension should be included, given by eq. 3.3:

$$q_V = \frac{1}{t_f - t_i} \left[\left((I_L - I_E) \left(1 - \left(\frac{D_{tube}}{D_{tank}} \right)^2 \right) \right) \frac{1}{\rho_w - \rho_a} \left(1 - \frac{\rho_a}{\rho_p} \right) [1 - \gamma(T - 20)] \right] + \delta q_{evp} \quad (3.3)$$

where q_m is the mass flow rate, q_v is the volume flow rate, m is the mass, t is the time, ρ_w is the density of liquid, ρ_a is the density of air, ρ_p is the density of standard weights, t_i is the start time, t_f is the end time, D_{tube} is the outer diameter of the tube, D_{tank} is the inner diameter of the weighing vessel and T is the temperature.

3.1.3. Test method

In a gravimetric microfluidic setup, an electronic balance is used to determine the delivered mass of a liquid from/through a test object (can be a flow generator or a flow meter). The time interval in which the mass is delivered, is determined by a timing module to deduct the mass flow rate. The climatic conditions – air temperature, relative humidity, and pressure are defined to correct for buoyancy effects on the balance in AAMI TIR 101 [3]. Liquid temperature is determined to convert mass flow rate to volume flow rate considering the density of the used fluid. At low flow rates, an oil layer can be applied to the surface of the delivered liquid to reduce the relative evaporation – mass delivery relationship.

Figure 5: gravimetric setup

3.1.4. Set up and test equipment

All the instruments used should be calibrated by an ISO17025 accredited laboratory or in an NMI/DI.

- **Balance**

The balance must have the capacity to measure the desired mass to deliver, depended on flow rate, required stability time, calibration time, and repetitions. The resolution and actuating resolution of the balance must correspond to the desired flow rate to be measured.

- **Timing module**

The timing module delivers a known accuracy of time synchronization related to the measured mass growth. Narrow calibration window places higher demands on the timing equipment.

- **Weighing vessel**

As for the balance, select the weighing vessel to manage the amount of liquid dispensed during an entire calibration sequence, considering pre-fill, flow rate, stabilization time etc.

- **Thermometer and ambient conditions**

The thermometer is utilized for the liquid temperature measurements to determine the density of the liquid. Where the ambient conditions are applied to determine stability of the ambient conditions and air density.

- **Calibration liquid**

According to ISO 3696 [5], the test solution should be either 0,9 % Normal Saline water or distilled water of minimum grade 3. If other clinically relevant liquids are used, the cause and impact must be considered carefully.

3.1.5. Consideration

- **Weighing vessel and needle**

The weighing vessel placed on the balance, to collect the liquid, must have well known and uniform dimensions since these have impact on the uncertainty contribution of needle buoyancy effect. The weighing vessel and needle must be clean to avoid undesired changes in surface tension and needle roughness.

- **Stabilization time**

The system requires time to settle and then stabilize after introducing a flow rate. To reduce the measurement fluctuations, it is necessary to exceed well past the settling time for the system, typically, 95% of the set flow rate must be reached before starting the measurements.

- **Liquid and ambient condition stability**

The stability of both the liquid and the ambient conditions has large impact on microfluidic measurements. Therefore they must be reduced as much as possible.

- **Evaporation**

The amount of evaporation from the surface of the liquid can affect the measurements, so the flow seems lower than reality. Therefore, it must be considered by either correcting for or reducing the evaporation, using for example an evaporation trap, or an oil layer on top of the weighed liquid.

- **Degasification**

If the calibration liquid does contain dissolved gas, it may cause measurement issues. Typically, the calibration liquid is degasified prior to calibration or inline during the calibration. Degasification can be performed using a commercial degasser, which is composed of a vacuum pump and a permeation membrane.

3.1.6. Main uncertainty contributions

The main standard uncertainties considered are: mass measurements (m), density of the mass pieces (ρ_B), density of the water (ρ_W), density of the air (ρ_A), evaporation rate (δQ_{evap}), water temperature (T), time (t), expansion coefficient (γ), standard deviation of the measurements (δQ_{rep}) and buoyancy on the immersed dispensing needle (δQ_{mbuoy}). [6]

Table 2 - Numerical example of the uncertainty components of the IPQ gravimetric facility

Uncertainty components $u(x_i)$		$u(x_i)$	Distribution	Evaluation	c_i	$(c_i \times x_i)^2$	ν_{eff}
$u(m_{ind.f})$	Final mass (g)	2.86E-05	Normal	B	1.06E-03	3.02927E-08	50000
$u(\rho_{w.b})$	Density of the water (g/ml)	6.21E-04	Rectangular	B	-2.60E-04	1.61314E-07	50
$u(\rho_a)$	Density of the air (g/ml)	2.89E-06	Rectangular	B	2.28E-04	6.56797E-10	50000
$u(\rho_c)$	Density of the mass pieces (g/ml)	2.50E-03	Normal	B	4.79E-09	1.19675E-11	50
$u(T)$	Temperature (°C)	7.02E-01	Normal	B	-2.59E-09	1.81839E-09	50

$u(\gamma_s)$	Expansion coefficient (/°C)	2.89E-07	Rectangular	B	-5.94E-04	1.71591E-10	50000
$u(m_{ind.i})$	Initial mass (g)	2.86E-05	Normal	B	-1.06E-03	3.02926E-08	50000
$u(Q_{Evap})$	Evaporation (g/ml)	1.47E-08	Rectangular	B	1.00E+00	1.46693E-08	50000
$u(t_f)$	Final time (s)	7.00E-04	Normal	B	2.74E-07	1.91629E-10	50
$u(t_i)$	Initial time (s)	7.00E-04	Normal	B	-2.74E-07	1.91629E-10	50
$u(\delta Q_{mbuoy})$ $\delta Q_{mbuoy} =$ $Q_w(d_i/d_b)^2$	Buoyancy (ml/s)	2.38193E-05	Normal	B	1.06E-03	2.52604E-08	50000
$u(\delta Q_{rep})$	Repeatability (ml/s)	1.22744E-06	Normal	A	1.00E+00	1.22744E-06	24
<i>Flow (ml/s)</i>	0.000259099						
<i>V_{eff}</i>	24.91998211						
<i>k</i>	2.11						
<i>Expanded uncertainty (ml/s)</i>	2.61409E-06						
<i>Expanded uncertainty (%)</i>	1.01						

3.1.7. Test protocol

1. Preparation

Dispose of all setup elements in the room where the test is to be performed, for at least 24 hours before beginning any measurement

2. Flushing the system

Dead volume in the system may cause entrapment of air and could compromise the integrity of the measurements. Therefore, the system must be flushed prior to calibration start up. Circulating the system with degasified liquid will in time absorb entrapped air. At low flow rates CO₂ and isopropanol are recognized methods to flush air from fluid systems. When flushed, run the system continuously with the calibration liquid until no flushing media is left.

3. Calibration start-up

Carefully prepare a clean weighing vessel with enough liquid to insert the needle. During preparation no liquid must be present on the walls. Place the container on the balance.

Insert the needle into a liquid layer in the container. The needle must be well below the water surface inside the container. However, the flow that exits the needle must not be located too close to the vessel's floor, since the inertia of the liquid is in risk of exerting an undesired force on the balance.

Measure the temperature at the liquid source reservoir and set the flow rate.

4. During the calibration

When the stabilization time is reached (typically, if the flow rate remains at +/-5% of its target value [3]), acquire mass, time, and ambient condition data continuously. Check the ambient conditions for fluctuations.

5. Calibration shutdown

When the calibration time is reached stop the acquisition and determine the temperature of the liquid in the container.

The number of repetitions should be at least 3 per flow rate.

3.2. Front tracking

3.2.1. Description of the test

The front tracking method for flow measurements is an optical method that consists of tracking the position of the meniscus of a liquid (liquid/air or liquid/liquid interface) inside a (typically) capillary tube over time. An optical image acquisition system and image processing software is used to achieve the position over time of the meniscus. Knowing the displacement of the meniscus over time and the cross-section area of the capillary, it is possible to calculate the flow rate. Alternatively, the front tracking method can be performed in a microfluidic channel if the inner dimensions of the channel are known along with their associated uncertainties.

3.2.2. Measurand

The fluid flowrate related to the front tracking method relates the optically acquired velocity of the fluid $\left(\frac{x_2-x_1}{\Delta t}\right)$ to the dimensions of the capillary tube (πr^2) . If the flow is measured inside a channel, replace (πr^2) by the channel's cross-section.

$$q_v = \frac{x_2-x_1}{\Delta t} \pi r^2 \quad (3.4)$$

where x_i is the position of the meniscus in the direction of the flow, Δt is the time interval between the positions, and r is the capillary section radius.

The capillary tube's material expansion property as a function of temperature $[1 - \gamma (T - 20)]$ is included to take deviation of the dimensions into account.

$$q_v = \frac{x_2-x_1}{\Delta t} \pi r^2 [1 - \gamma (T - 20)] \quad (3.5)$$

where q_v is the volume flow rate, γ is the capillary material coefficient of expansion, T is the calibration liquid temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$).

Similarly, the liquid's thermal expansion during the measurement should be evaluated using equation 3.5.

3.2.3. Test method

The test method relies on three stages: calibration of the camera (determining the pixel size), image processing, and determination of position of the meniscus.

- The calibration of the camera determines the relationship between dimensions of a known and calibrated object (for example the outer diameter of the capillary) and pixels of an image. Usually, the output of the camera's calibration is the pixel size in microns (μm).

Figure 6: camera calibration using capillary's outer diameter

Figure 7: camera calibration using a standard (micrometer object from Olympus)

- Image processing facilitates the identification of contours which makes the meniscus available for accurate positioning. Image processing includes image segmentation, digital image correlation, correction for misalignment, etc.
- The determination of the position of the meniscus is identified by software tools able to find coordinates of the meniscus, either at reference point(s) along its contour or its average position along the flow direction. Meniscus positions are determined for each successive

images. The meniscus velocity is calculated as the time derivative (global or on a defined sliding time window) of its successive timestamped positions.

Figure 8: determination of the position of the meniscus

3.2.4. Setup and test equipment

All the instruments used should be calibrated by an accredited laboratory or an NMI/DI.

A typical setup may include:

- Capillary tube (or any other tubing or channel of known dimensions with associated uncertainties)
- High resolution camera
- image processing software

Figure 9: example of a front tracking setup for micro and nano flow measurements and calibrations

3.2.5. Main uncertainty contributions

The main standard uncertainties considered related to the front tracking method are: meniscus displacement, $u(\Delta x)$; time interval between frames, $u(\Delta t)$; capillary radius, $u(r)$; water temperature, $u(T_w)$; material expansion, $u(\gamma)$; stability, $u(\delta Q_{sta})$; standard deviation of the measurements $u(\delta Q_{rep})$. [7]

Table 3 - The estimated contribution for the front tracking method

Uncertainty components	Estimation	$u(x_i)$	c_i	$(c_i \times x_i)^2$
Meniscus displacement (mm)	11.76	1.50×10^{-02}	2.35×10^{-02}	1.25×10^{-07}
Radius (mm)	0.575	1.47×10^{-03}	9.63×10^{-01}	2.01×10^{-06}
Time (s)	44.107	2.97×10^{-03}	-6.28×10^{-03}	3.48×10^{-10}
Repeatability ($\mu\text{L/s}$)	0.0013	0.0013	1	1.80×10^{-06}
Stability ($\mu\text{L/s}$)	1.37×10^{-04}	1.37×10^{-04}	1	1.88×10^{-08}
Expansion coefficient ($/^{\circ}\text{C}$)	0.00024	6.92×10^{-06}	-8.14×10^{-01}	3.18×10^{-11}
Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	22.94	0.005	-2.77×10^{-06}	1.92×10^{-16}
Flow rate ($\mu\text{L/h}$)	997.1	U_{comb} ($\mu\text{L/h}$)	7.2	
V_{eff}	100.15	k	2.02	
U_{exp} ($\mu\text{L/h}$)	15	U (%)	1.5	

3.2.6. Test protocol

1. Preparation

Dispose of all setup elements in the room where the test is to be performed, for at least 24 hours before beginning any measurement

2. Flushing the system

Dead volume in the system may cause entrapment of air and could compromise the integrity of the measurements. Therefore, the system must be flushed prior to calibration start up. Circulating the system with degasified liquid will in time absorb entrapped air. At low flow rates CO_2 and isopropanol are recognized methods to flush air from fluid systems. When flushed, run the system continuously with the calibration liquid until no flushing media is left.

3. Calibration start-up

Position the calibrated camera in front of the capillary's (or channel) section in which the meniscus will flow. Adjust the lighting, so that the image has the best contrast for the exposure time that will be used for the measurement. Make sure that the capillary is in focus and align it with the image bottom or top border so that it appears horizontal in the image.

Measure the temperature at the liquid source reservoir and set the flow rate.

4. During the calibration

When the stabilization time is reached (typically, if the flow rates is remains at $\pm 5\%$ of its target value), acquire timestamped images, and ambient condition data continuously. Check the ambient conditions for fluctuations. If dynamic (fluctuating) flows are to be measured, make sure to choose a framerate sufficiently high (typically equal or superior to 1 frame per second - 1 fps).

5. Calibration shutdown

When the calibration time is reached stop the image acquisition and ambient conditions recording.

6. Image processing & flow rate calculation

Apply image processing to determine the meniscus positions in each successive image, and calculate the flow as the time derivative of the meniscus' positions.

The number of repetitions should be at least 3 per flow rate.

3.3. Displacement methods

High precision syringe pumps with glass or metal syringes or piston provers, can be used to achieve an accurate flowrate for calibration and testing of Instruments. Flow is generated by the piston prover/syringe pump and the value compared with the results given by instrument under test .

The syringe pump/piston prover needs to be calibrated on a primary gravimetric standard or calibrate directly the geometrical dimensions as well as the speed and position of the plunger in order to establish traceability to the SI unit system. One of these techniques is the interferometric method.

3.3.1. Interferometric method

The Interferometric method [8] uses an interferometer (Hewlett-Packard, model 5528A; it operates at 633 nm, and the signal is processed using a LabVIEW application) to monitor the distance travelled by a pusher block of the syringe pump in order to determine the flow rate. The use of interferometry for flow measurement involved the use of the following components: a laser unit (A) with a detector incorporated (an optical arrangement composed by two retroreflector cubes (C) (one of which with a beam splitter attached), a Control Unit, a pusher block, the syringe pump with the removable plastic syringe , (Figure 5).

Figure 10: example of a interferometer setup for micro and nano flow measurements and calibrations

3.3.2. Measurand

In practice, the generation of flow was accomplished by a stepper motor which drove a screw connected to a pusher block that itself pushed the syringe piston. Therefore, knowing the internal diameter of the syringe with very high precision, the travelled distance, and the time needed for that travelled distance, it was possible to calculate the flow rate of the fluid inside the syringe and its uncertainty. The flowrate can be determined with the following equation:

$$Q = v \times A = \frac{x_2 - x_1}{\Delta t} \times \pi r^2 = \frac{d\pi r^2}{t} \quad (3.6)$$

where Q is flowrate, v is velocity, A is area, x are the start and end distance, Δt is the measured time, r is the syringe radius, and d is the distance.

3.3.3. Main uncertainty contributions

The main standard uncertainties considered are: distance (d), time (t), radius of the syringe (r), stability of the setup (δQ_{sta}), water temperature (T), time (t), expansion coefficient (γ), standard deviation of the measurements (δQ_{rep}). [9]

Table 4 - The estimated contribution for the interferometric method

Uncertainty components	Estimation	$u(x_i)$	c_i	$(c_i \times x_i)^2$
Distance (mm)	0.316	1.85×10^{-4}	9.5×10^{-4}	3.1×10^{-14}
Time (s)	17490	7.0×10^{-4}	-1.7×10^{-8}	3.62×10^{-21}
Radius (mm)	2.3	5×10^{-3}	2.6×10^{-4}	1.71×10^{-12}
Temperature (°C)	20.47	5×10^{-5}	-3.01×10^{-9}	2.26×10^{-22}
Expansion coefficient (°C)	1.0×10^{-5}	2.88×10^{-8}	-1.22×10^{-2}	1.23×10^{-19}
Stability ($\mu\text{L/s}$)	0	6.69×10^{-7}	1	4.48×10^{-13}
Repeatability ($\mu\text{L/s}$)	0	4.70×10^{-6}	1	2.21×10^{-11}
Flow ($\mu\text{L/s}$)	3.01×10^{-4}			
Flow ($\mu\text{L/h}$)	1.083			
u_{comb} ($\mu\text{L/s}$)	4.9×10^{-6}			
v_{eff}	657.20			
k	2.0			
U_{exp} ($\mu\text{L/s}$)	9.9×10^{-6}			
U_{exp} ($\mu\text{L/h}$)	0.036			

3.3.4. Test protocol

The tests using the interferometer were performed at different flow rates using the following conditions:

- Acclimatization time of 24 h, all the instruments and the water stood in the same room for 24 h;
- Controlled room temperature equal to $(20 \pm 3) \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$;
- Room temperature variation during the measurements not more than $1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.
- Humidity room above 50 %;
- Glass or plastic syringes of different volumes depending on the flow generator used;

f) Before any measurement starts, it was important to prime the syringe and all the tubing and ensures no entrapped air in the system;

g) All travelled distance values were directly obtained from the control unit of the interferometer using a LABVIEW application;

h) Time measured by the computer using LABVIEW traceable to a calibrated digital chronometer by direct comparison or a time stamp;

i) The distance was collected every 30 s; in some cases, 10 s was used;

j) Ultra-pure water was used as calibration liquid, with a conductivity of 0.05 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$;

k) Tests were performed for at least for 30 min.

During the tests, the temperature of the water and the air, the relative humidity and the atmospheric pressure need to be continually measured and recorded.

The number of repetitions should be at least 3 per flow rate.

3.4. Secondary methods

Flow rate can be measured using a dedicated flow meter. Commercially available flow meters for low flow rates are mainly based on the following principles:

- Coriolis
- Thermal difference
- Pressure differential

A flow meter is used by placing the instrument in series with the system, device, or object (such as a tube or channel) through which the liquid flows. The flow measurement accuracy can be influenced by liquid properties changes (such as the liquid density), ambient conditions changes, and any other influence factor which may affects the flow or the measuring device performances. In any case, the calibration of the flow meter is required in order to know the measurement accuracy.

3.4.1. Coriolis Flowmeter (ISO 10790:2015)

Coriolis flowmeters operate on the principle that inertia forces are generated whenever a particle in a rotating body moves relative to the body in a direction towards or away from the center of rotation. This inertial force is called the Coriolis force.

A Coriolis flowmeter is an electromechanical system which consists of a flow sensor and a transmitter. The Coriolis flowmeter sensor is the primary mechanical part while the transmitter provides control and signal processing.

Coriolis flowmeters directly measure fluid mass flow rate and density at metering conditions. However, there are applications where the advantages of a Coriolis flowmeter would be very beneficial, but the desired measurement is volume at metering conditions. Coriolis flowmeters can be effectively used for volume flow measurement.

Calibration by using Coriolis flowmeter:

The flow shall be kept stable to within $\pm 5\%$ of the selected flow rate for the duration of the calibration test at that flow rate. Variations in fluid temperature and pressure should be minimized during the

calibration process. For a single run, the temperature should be held constant to within 1 °C, and to within 5 °C for the entire duration of the calibration. The fluid pressure within the test rig should be kept sufficiently high to avoid flashing or cavitation in the flowmeter and/or in the vicinity of the flowmeter. Depending on the Coriolis flowmeter design, the performance can be affected by variations in fluid density and viscosity. In these cases, test fluids should be used having properties that are the same or similar to the process fluid for which the flowmeter is intended.

3.4.2. Thermal Mass Flowmeter (ISO 14511:2019)

TMF meters generally use for gas and fall into two basic design categories:

- a) capillary TMF meters (CTMF meters);
- b) full bore TMF meters, consisting of the following two types (ITMF meter):
 - 1) insertion type
 - 2) in-line type

A typical CTMF meter consists of a meter body and flow sensor. The flow sensor is mounted integrally into the meter body. A defined portion of the gas flow from the meter body is diverted through the (bypass) flow sensor, through which the gas flowrate is measured. TMF meter is often combined with a flow controller downstream to the sensing sensor to obtain a mass flow controller.

A typical ITMF flowmeter consists of two temperature sensors. An amount of heating power P is applied to one of the sensors, causing its temperature to rise to a measured value T_2 . The other sensor measures the gas temperature T_1 . The gas mass flowrate can be determined from the temperature difference between the heated sensor and the gas ($\Delta T = T_2 - T_1$) and the amount of heating power P applied.

3.4.3. Pressure Differential Flowmeter (ISO 5167-1:2003)

The principle of the method of measurement is based on the installation of a primary device (such as orifice plate, a nozzle or a venturi tube) into a pipeline in which a fluid is running full. The installation of the primary device causes a static pressure difference between the upstream side and the throat or downstream side of the device. The flowrate can be determined from the measured value of this pressure difference and from the knowledge of the characteristics of the flowing fluid as well as the circumstances under which the device is being used.

The mass flowrate can be determined, since it is related to the differential pressure:

$$q_m = \frac{C}{\sqrt{1-\beta^4}} \varepsilon \frac{\pi}{4} d^2 \sqrt{2\Delta p \rho_1} \quad (3.7)$$

Except for the case of venturi tubes, C may be dependent on Re , which is itself dependent on q_m . In such cases the final value of C , and hence q_m , must be obtained by iteration.

The cavitation and compressibility effects are important for the pressure differential flowmeter in microflow. The orifice cavitation number σ is defined as:

$$\sigma = \frac{2(P_{down} - P_v)}{\rho V^2} \quad (3.8)$$

where P_{down} is the static pressure downstream the orifice and P_v is the local vapor pressure. The threshold is $\sigma \approx 0.3$ needed to start cavitation in micro-orifice liquid flows. The cavitation number should be higher than threshold.

The relevance of compressibility effects was checked with the Mach number defined as:

$$Ma = \frac{V}{a_s} \quad (3.9)$$

where a_s is the liquid sound velocity. The Mach number should be below of 0,3 to neglect compressibility effects and assume incompressible flow conditions [8].

The pressure differential flowmeters need constant flowrates, not pulsating flow. The flow is considered as not being pulsating when

$$\frac{\Delta p'_{ms}}{\Delta p} \leq 0,1 \quad (3.10)$$

where $\Delta p'$ is the fluctuating component of the differential pressure, Dp'_{ms} is the root mean square value of $\Delta p'$.

$\Delta p'$ can only be measured accurately using a fast-response differential pressure sensor [ISO 5167-1:2003].

4. Volume

4.1. Gravimetric weighing

4.1.1. Description of the test

The gravimetric method is the standard method used both by National Metrology Institutes (NMIs) and by accredited laboratories to calibrate volume instruments. The method consists of weighing the instrument under calibration when empty and again when full with an appropriate liquid. The difference obtained in the weighing measurements gives the mass of contained or delivered liquid.

4.1.2. Measurand

For the conversion of the balance reading of the mass m to volume V at the reference temperature, a correction for the liquid's density and air buoyancy is necessary. The calculation of the liquid volume at the reference temperature is given in the following equation [10]:

$$V_{ref} = (I_L - I_E) \times \frac{1}{\rho_W - \rho_A} \times \left(1 - \frac{\rho_A}{\rho_B}\right) \times [1 - \gamma(t_W - t_{ref})] \quad (4.1)$$

where V_{ref} is the calculated volume at the reference temperature, in ml; I_L is the balance reading of the weighing vessel after liquid delivery, in g; I_E is the balance reading of the weighing vessel before liquid delivery, in g ($I_E = 0$ in case the balance was tared with the weighing vessel); ρ_A is the density of air, in g/ml, [11]; ρ_B is the actual or assumed density of the weights¹ used to calibrate the balance, in g/ml; ρ_W is density of water, in g/ml [12]; γ is the coefficient of cubic thermal expansion of the material of which the volumetric instrument tested is made, in reciprocal degrees Celsius; t_W is the temperature of the water used in the test, in degrees Celsius; and t_{ref} is the reference temperature, in degrees Celsius.

The equation for air density can be used at temperatures between 15 °C and 27 °C, barometric pressure between 600 hPa and 1 100 hPa, and relative humidity between 20 % and 80 % [11].

$$\rho_A = \frac{1}{1000} \times \frac{0,34848 \times P - 0,009 \times h_r \times 10^{(0,061 \times t)}}{t + 273,15} \quad (4.2)$$

where ρ_A is the air density, in g/ml; t is the ambient temperature, in °C; P is the barometric pressure, in hPa; h_r is the relative air humidity, in %. The relative uncertainty of this formula is 2.4×10^{-4} .

The density of pure water is usually calculated using formula given in the literature [12]. Tanaka formula, provides a good basis for standardization:

$$\rho_W = a_5 \times \left[1 - \frac{(t_W + a_1)^2 \times (t_W + a_2)}{a_3 \times (t_W + a_4)}\right] \quad (4.3)$$

where ρ_W is the density of water, in g/ml; t_W is the water temperature, in °C; $a_1 = -3,983035$ °C; $a_2 = 301,797$ °C; $a_3 = 522528,9$ (°C)²; $a_4 = 69,34881$ °C; and $a_5 = 0,999974950$ g/ml

4.1.3. Equipment requirements (can be used the ones described in ISO 8655)
All the instruments used should be calibrated by an accredited laboratory or an NMI/DI.

- **Balance**

The balance must have the capacity to measure the desired mass to deliver, depended on volume. The resolution and uncertainty of the balance must correspond to the volume to be measured.

- **Weighing vessel**

As for the balance, select the weighing vessel to manage the amount of liquid dispensed during an entire calibration sequence.

¹ Stainless steel weights of density 8,0 g/ml are typically used for balance calibration.

- **Thermometer and ambient conditions**

The thermometer is utilized for the liquid temperature measurements to determine the density of the liquid. Where the ambient conditions are applied to determine stability of the ambient conditions and air density.

- **Calibration liquid**

According to ISO 3696 [5], the test solution should distilled water of minimum grade 3. If other clinically relevant liquids are used, the cause and impact must be considered carefully.

4.1.4. Other Considerations

- **Equipment, liquid and ambient condition stability**

The stability of both the instruments, the liquid and the ambient conditions has large impact on microfluidic measurements. Therefore they must be reduced as much as possible.

- **Evaporation**

The size of evaporation from the surface of the liquid can affect the measurements, so the volume seems lower than reality. Therefore, it must be considered by either correcting for or reducing the evaporation by the use of an evaporation trap in the balance.

4.1.5. Main uncertainty contributions

The main uncertainty contributions for the volume gravimetric method can be found in EURAMET cg 19 [13]. They are mass, water temperature, water density, air density, density of reference weights, cubic thermal expansion coefficient of the material of the instrument under calibration, operator effect, evaporation, measurement repeatability.

Table 5 - The estimated contribution for volume determination

Uncertainty components	Estimation	$u(x_i)$	c_i	$(c_i \times x_i)^2$
Mass (mg)	0.1965	2.72E-03	1.00E+00	2.73E-03
Density of the reference weights mg/ μ L	8.00	3.46E-02	3.62E-06	1.26E-07
Water density mg/ μ L	0.9980	2.88E-05	-1.98E-01	-5.70E-06
Air density g/mL	0.0012	1.10E-06	1.73E-01	1.90E-07
Coefficient of thermal expansion from material $^{\circ}$ C ⁻¹	2.40E-04	6.93E-06	-0.168487512	-1.17E-06
Temperature $^{\circ}$ C	20.86	3.42E-01	-4.73E-05	-1.62E-05
Operator effect (μ L)	0	1.46E-03	1.00E+00	0.0014586
Evaporation (μ L)	0	1.13E-04	1.00E+00	1.13E-04

Measurement Repeatability (μL)	0	5.77E-04	1.00E+00	0.0005774
Volume (μL)	0.197			
u_c	3.1E-03			
k	2.01			
U	0.006			

4.1.6. Test protocol

The tests using the gravimetric method for volume determination were performed the following conditions:

- a) Acclimatization time of 24 h, all the instruments and the water stood in the same room for 24 h;
- b) Controlled room temperature equal to $(20 \pm 3) ^\circ\text{C}$;
- c) Room temperature variation during the measurements not more than $1 ^\circ\text{C}$.
- d) Humidity room above 50 %;
- e) Weight the empty and dry microchip
- f) Measure the water temperature
- g) Fill the microchip with water ensuring no bubbles are inside
- h) Weight the chip full of water

During the tests, the temperature of the water and the air, the relative humidity and the atmospheric pressure need to be continually measured and recorded.

The number of repetitions should be at least 5.

5. Volume of droplets

The amount of liquid dispensed by an instrument and the size of its drop depends on the dosing velocity, the liquid, and the size of the nozzle for the dispensing instrument. Several methods apply to determining a drop volume, namely gravimetry, photometry, fluorescence, and new methods based on optical technology have been developed [14].

5.1. Gravimetric

The drop can be weight after is delivered from the instrument under test into a balance with an evaporation trap. The procedure is similar to the calibration of a micropipette described in ISO 8655. The equation and apparatus are similar to the information described above for volume determination of microchips.

5.2. Optical method(s)

The droplet size can be determined by imaging liquid droplets in flight by a suitable digital optical setup, such as a calibrated high-speed camera or a stroboscopic imaging system. From the acquired grey-scale images of the droplet, the size and shape of the outline of the droplet is determined by conversion to a black and white image by the image processing algorithm. The three-dimensional volume of the droplet is then reconstructed by rotating the two-dimensional projection extracted from the image around the axis defined by the flight path of the droplet, assuming rotational symmetry of the droplet shape.

Figure 11: example of an optical setup for drop measurements

5.2.1. Main uncertainty contributions

The main uncertainty contributions are: volume determination $u(V)$; time $u(t)$; water evaporation $u(\delta Q_{evap})$; standard deviation of the mean volume (δQ_{rep}). [15]

5.2.2. Test protocols

The tests for all the setups used should be performed at the following conditions.

- a) Acclimatization time of 24 h, all the instruments and the water stood in the same room for 24 h;
- b) Controlled room temperature equal to $(20 \pm 3) ^\circ\text{C}$;
- c) Humidity room above 50 %;
- d) Prime the instrument under test and all the tubing and ensures no entrapped air in the system;
- e) The drop pictures were taken every 30 s; in some cases, 10 s was used depending on the size of the drop which is proportional to the flow rate; The volume is determined by using the appropriated software.
- f) Ultra-pure water was used as calibration liquid, with a conductivity of $0.05 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$.

During the tests, the temperature of the water and the air, the relative humidity and the atmospheric pressure need to be continually measured and recorded.

The number of repetitions should be at least 5.

6. References

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